

Human-Aware Motion Planner for Collaborative Transportation of Flexible Materials

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Abstract. In industrial environments like factories and warehouses, transportation of flexible materials that need the collaboration of several subjects is a typical activity. One instance is the handling of enormous fibre sheets in the fabrication of composite parts, which presents several difficulties, including handling flexible materials and needing to place the material with extreme precision. Recently, there has been a lot of interest in employing robots to help human workers carry such things. However, this typically entails the robot adopting a follower attitude just intended for passive support without fully using its accuracy and repeatability. To make the best possible use of the robot's and the operator's skills, it is necessary to use an intelligent motion planner that takes into account the ergonomics of the operator but at the same time ensures the precision required by the task. In this paper, we present a preliminary study for a Human-Aware Motion Planner for the cooperative transportation of materials.

Keywords: Human-robot cooperation, human-aware motion planner, flexible material transportation, composite parts manufacturing.

1 Introduction

One of the most critical activities in the textile and composite part manufacturing landscape is the Human-Robot cooperative transportation of flexible materials [5]. Large pieces are typically utilized to shape a component, and in current production lines, they are handled manually by two or more workers: they pick up the piece by hand off a table and bring it to the tooling station. The accurate placement of the cut-piece is a demanding requirement due to the high positioning requirements and the size of the piece. This results in non-ergonomic handling positions for the workers and high process times, motivating the introduction of a robotic partner to alleviate operator fatigue and improve efficiency. The robot has to act as a smart assistant, following the user while ensuring an ergonomic position and preventing material damage. At the same time, it must be able to take an active role by guiding the user when high accuracy is needed (for instance, to guarantee the proper fiber orientation).

Many works in the literature focus on the co-transportation of flexible materials where the robot only follows the operator [2, 10, 12]. In situations when precise material placement is necessary, a pure follower robot cannot offer the greatest support to the operator

Fig. 1: An example of human-robot cooperative transport.

since it can only respond to human actions, and it may be challenging and unpleasant for the human operator to manoeuvre the robot into the desired position. To be able to respond to this problem, it is necessary to use a high-level planner who can help the two agents accomplish the task. Recent works on this type of motion planner are oriented towards maintaining the ergonomics of the operator, but they only considered rigid materials [7, 13] or the reconfiguration of the robot itself [3, 11]. However, these approaches do not completely satisfy the requirements of flexible material transport in composite parts manufacturing. To overcome the limitations and improve these approaches for a more challenging scenario, we propose in this paper a preliminary study for a Human-Aware Motion Planner able to guarantee ergonomic transportation of flexible material and a final place precision. This challenge is addressed within the EU project DrapeBot (<https://www.drapebot.eu/>), which attempts to create an HRC system capable of aiding an operator working on carbon fibre draping. Figure 1 depicts an example of the human-robot cooperative transport to be achieved in the DrapeBot project.

2 System Concept

As described in the previous paragraph, the proposed method aims to go beyond the current approaches. The robot must not only passively support the user but also actively direct him to the desired position while avoiding collisions with obstacles in the environment and keeping to ergonomic boundaries for the operator. We propose a Human-Aware Motion Planner based on online and offline components to fulfil these demands. The offline module is responsible for computing an ergonomic path that serves as a high-level guideline for the robot and the operator. However well the calculated trajectory may satisfy ergonomic constraints, the operator may prefer not to follow this trajectory completely (as if he were a pure follower of the robot). For this reason, the online component is necessary: its task is to accommodate the deformations introduced by the user while ensuring the required accuracy in the place phase. However, deformations introduced by the operator can lead to collisions with environmental obstacles. This makes using a third module necessary to ensure the robot does not collide. A deformation volume estimation algorithm is therefore needed for this purpose. The Human-

Fig. 2: Human-Aware Motion Planner overview.

Aware Motion Planner uses information from an external vision system that perceives the environment and the user's movements and models them via a skeleton. Thanks to the skeleton, the ergonomic path (offline module) and the online deformation can be computed.

2.1 Ergonomic Motion Planner

The planner must consider human constraints to determine the best possible trajectory. Only user arm position restrictions are considered in this first phase regarding ergonomic limitations. This suggests that the user's effort is considered for the transportation job. For example, when the user raises his arms over his head, he exerts more effort than when he raises his arms at hip level. Based on this idea, it is feasible to compute the user's height and the maximum and least accessible height of the arms using the skeleton tracker given by the vision camera system. Upper and lower achievable height limitations are produced based on this information. The limits are generated using values along the z-axis (the axis that points up). The outside zone is eliminated as non-ergonomic, while the inner zone is split further and connected with a cost function. As the limitations are approached, the cost increases linearly. The ultimate goal is reducing the cost function to achieve a low-effort path representing the best possible ergonomic path.

2.2 Collision-free Volume Estimation

Given the nominal ergonomic path obtained by the motion planner, it is possible to forward it directly to the online deformation module. However, a collision-free region around the nominal trajectory is estimated to increase safety during deformation [8]. The collision-free volume is a part of the space where the robot changed its nominal path in reaction to human activities without colliding with the other items in the workcell. The algorithm that computes the deformation boundaries has a linear computational complexity and will be entirely performed offline in the joint space, thus without occupying computational time for the online control during execution. The overall concept is to generate a volume which synthesizes the whole workspace but is left free in the space surrounding the nominal path and near the goal. Then, the boundaries defining the final intervals are found by observing for which joints the robot collides with such volume values.

Fig. 3: Representation of the Ergonomic Motion Planner on the left and Deformation boundaries limits on the right.

2.3 Trajectory Deformation

Various approaches can be followed to deform the motion of a robot. [1,9] focused on how the material deforms during the motion of the robot and operator. Other techniques focused on the controller robot side like [4,6]. We believe that an approach based on Artificial Potential Fields (APFs) [6] is the best one to meet the needs of cooperative human-robot transportation. In addition, the combination of the offline approach with the APF enables the robot to move independently, adjusting to the dynamic environment and successfully reacting to unanticipated changes (i.e., moving obstacles) while assuring the operator's safety and high-level job precision and accuracy.

3 Conclusions

This paper presents a preliminary study about Human-Aware Motion Planner for the Human-Robot cooperative transportation of flexible materials. This approach is under development in a real industrial application like draping fiber carbon pieces within the EU project DrapeBot. Preliminary results are showing good results both in terms of offline module computation. The offline modules are evaluated by the planning time less than $500ms$ and a collision-free confidence factor equal to 92%. The confidence factor aims to express the quality of the boundaries produced. Concerning the online component of the framework, no quantitative results have yet been achieved to validate the approach.

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